

assigned to $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ modes, respectively ¹²⁻¹⁴.

The infrared spectral studies thus indicate that SEC behaves as a uninegative tridentate ligand in all the complexes except in $Cu(SEC-2H)_2 \cdot H_2O$ where it is binegative tridentate.

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Complex Formation Between Some Transition Metal Ions and Phenetsal

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PHENETSAL (*p*-acetylaminophenyl salicylate) is analgetic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic and tuberculostatic. Because of these characteristics, the studies on the metal ion complexes of phenetsal were undertaken^{1,2}. The stabilities of the complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with phenetsal are reported here. Bjerrum-Calvin^{3,4} *pH* titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁵ has been used for the study,

Experimental

Phenetsal was synthesised by reported method⁶. It was purified and dissolved in absolute alcohol to get a 0.02 *M* solution.

The metal salts used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. Their solutions were prepared in water and standardised to 0.01 *M*. The aqueous 0.05 *M* HClO₄ was standardised against a standard alkali. One molar aqueous solution of NaClO₄ was used to maintain the required ionic strength. Carbonate free 0.1 *M* KOH was used for *pH* metric titrations.

A Sisco made water thermostat, type TBS, fitted with an electric stirrer, heater and toluene regulator, was used to maintain the temperature constant. The *pH* metric titrations were run with a Systronics *pH* meter, model 322-1 fitted with glass and calomel electrodes assembly. The following three titrations were performed with the standard alkali.

- A. Mineral acid alone.
- B. A + ligand solution.
- C. B + metal ion solution.

The total initial volume in all titrations was 20.00 ml in alcohol-water 70 : 30 (v/v). As the titrations were carried out in alcohol-water system, the correct values of *pH* were obtained by appropriate correction⁷. The curves were plotted between the volume of alkali added and *pH* reached.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\bar{n}$ and *pL* were calculated by Irving and Rossotti method⁸. The values of stability constants were calculated by linear extrapolation and half $\bar{n}$ methods⁸. The average values of stability constants in log units are given in Table I. The values of thermodynamic stability constants were obtained by plotting $\log k_s$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolating to zero ionic strength. The values of free energy change (ΔG) associated with complex formation were obtained by the relation

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K$$

These values are also given in Table I. The stability of the complexes are in the order $Cu^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Mn^{2+}$. This order can be explained on the basis of increasing second ionization potential and electronegativity values and decreasing ionic radii in the same transition metal series. The crystal field stabilization energy plays important role in enhancing the stability of the complexes in the case of ions other than Mn^{2+} . The stability order found here agrees with the Irving and Williams order⁹.

The values of stability constants record a decrease with rise of temperature and ionic strength of the medium. Low temperature, therefore, is favourable for complexation.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANT AND FREE ENERGY DATA OF PHENETSAL COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTHS IN ALCOHOL-WATER SYSTEM, (70 : 30 v/v)

Metal ion	Temp. °C	Ionic strength	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	-ΔG ₁ k cal/mole	-ΔG ₂ k cal/mole	-ΔG* k cal/mole
Mn ⁺⁺	25	0.00	5.52	5.18	10.70	7.53	7.06	14.59
		0.05	5.05	4.64	9.69	6.89	6.33	13.22
		0.10	4.89	4.01	8.90	6.67	5.47	12.14
		0.20	4.69	3.83	8.52	6.40	5.22	11.62
	35	0.10	4.44	3.63	8.07	6.26	5.12	11.38
	45	0.10	4.23	3.50	7.73	6.16	5.09	11.25
Co ⁺⁺	25	0.00	5.65	5.20	10.85	7.70	7.09	14.79
		0.05	5.22	4.78	10.00	7.12	6.29	13.41
		0.10	5.02	4.61	9.63	6.85	6.29	13.14
		0.20	4.82	4.42	9.24	6.57	6.03	12.60
	35	0.10	4.67	3.99	8.66	6.58	5.62	12.20
	45	0.10	4.50	3.72	8.22	6.55	5.41	11.96
Ni ⁺⁺	25	0.00	5.84	5.40	11.24	7.96	7.36	15.33
		0.05	5.49	4.90	10.39	7.49	6.68	14.17
		0.10	5.32	4.73	10.05	7.13	6.45	13.58
		0.20	5.10	4.32	9.42	6.95	5.89	12.84
	35	0.10	4.93	4.14	9.07	6.95	5.84	12.79
	45	0.10	4.86	3.96	8.82	7.07	5.76	12.53
Cu ⁺⁺	25	0.00	7.08	5.84	12.92	9.65	7.96	17.62
		0.05	6.22	5.07	11.29	8.48	6.91	15.40
		0.10	5.66	4.90	10.56	7.72	6.68	14.40
		0.20	5.35	4.52	9.87	7.30	6.16	13.46
	35	0.10	5.17	4.33	9.50	7.29	6.11	13.39
	45	0.10	5.00	4.16	9.16	7.28	6.07	13.33

*ΔG = ΔG₁ + ΔG₂.

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Physico-chemical Studies on Ag(I) Benzamidothiosemicarbazide Complex

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INTERACTION between Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) with benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) has been reported earlier^{1,2}. The composition and structural characteristics of BTSC complex of Ag(I)

have since been studied and the results are reported here.

Experimental

Fresh solutions of BTSC³ and AgNO₃ were always used. The strength of AgNO₃ solution was determined by the usual method.

Conductometric titrations of BTSC against Ag(I) were carried out to determine the metal-ligand ratio. A series of solutions keeping BTSC concentration constant and varying [Ag⁺] (direct titration) and vice-versa (reverse titration) were prepared keeping the volume constant in each case. The plots of conductance vs concentration of metal (or ligand) gave inflections corresponding to the stoichiometric ratio. Philips conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell (cell constant 0.62) was used for determining the conductance.

Amperometric titrations were carried out on a manual polarograph in conjunction with a Pye Scalamp galvanometer. Both direct and reverse titrations were carried out using 2.0 × 10⁻² M solution of the metal and the ligand in presence of 0.2 M KNO₃ as supporting electrolyte and 0.008% gelatin as maximum suppressor. Solutions were deaerated with purified N₂ gas. The titrations were carried out at -0.1 volts applied on d.m.e. using SCE as reference electrode. The corrected values for dilution factor of current were plotted against the volume of metal or ligand. The inflection point gave the stoichiometric ratio.

Elico pH-meter using glass electrode in conjunction with SCE was used for pH-metric measurements. Standard solution of KOH was prepared in